

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES
SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**"IN SITU GELLING DRUG DELIVERY SYSTEMS:
MECHANISMS, POLYMERS, EVALUATION AND
PHARMACEUTICAL APPLICATIONS – A
COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW"**

Vinay Tripathi, Prashant Maithil, Satkar Prasad

RKDF School of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Bhabha University, Bhopal (M.P.)

Mail id: vinaysdr2017@gmail.com

Abstract:

In situ gel systems have emerged as a promising and innovative approach in controlled and sustained drug delivery. These systems are administered as liquids and undergo a phase transition from sol to gel under physiological conditions such as changes in temperature, pH, ionic concentration, or enzymatic activity. The unique sol-to-gel transformation enhances drug residence time, improves bioavailability, reduces dosing frequency, and increases patient compliance. Various natural and synthetic polymers, including pectin, gellan gum, alginic acid, chitosan, xanthan gum, guar gum, carbopol, hydroxypropyl methylcellulose (HPMC), xyloglucan, and poloxamers, have been extensively employed in the development of in situ gelling formulations. Depending on the triggering mechanism, in situ gels may be classified as temperature-sensitive, pH-sensitive, ion-activated, enzymatically cross-linked, or photo-polymerized systems. These formulations have found wide applications in oral, ocular, nasal, rectal, vaginal, injectable, dermal, and transdermal drug delivery. In situ gel systems offer several advantages over conventional dosage forms, including prolonged drug release, enhanced therapeutic efficacy, improved stability, reduced systemic side effects, and better patient acceptability. The present review highlights the mechanisms of in situ gelation, various polymers used in formulation development, applications in different routes of administration, and important evaluation parameters. Owing to their versatility, biocompatibility, and effectiveness, in situ gels represent a promising platform for future controlled drug delivery systems.

Keywords: *In Situ Gel, Sol-Gel Transition, Controlled Drug Delivery, Sustained Release, Thermosensitive Gel, Gellan Gum, Carbopol, Chitosan, HPMC, Poloxamer, Ocular Drug Delivery.*

Corresponding author:

Vinay Tripathi,

RKDF School of Pharmaceutical Sciences,

Bhabha University, Bhopal (M.P.)

Mail id: vinaysdr2017@gmail.com

QR CODE

Please cite this article in press Vinay Tripathi et al., In Situ Gelling Drug Delivery Systems: Mechanisms, Polymers, Evaluation And Pharmaceutical Applications – A Comprehensive Review, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2026; 13(06).

INTRODUCTION:

The 'in situ gel' system has emerged as one of the best novel drug delivery systems, the in situ gelling system helps for the sustained and controlled release of the drugs, improved patient compliance and comfort by its special characteristic feature of 'Sol to Gel' transition. In situ gelling system is a formulation that is in solution form before entering in to the body, but it will change to gel form under various physiological conditions. The sol to gel transition depends on various factors like temperature, change in pH, solvent exchange, UV radiation, and presence of specific molecules or ions. The drug delivery systems having the above mentioned properties 'sol to gel transition' can be widely used for sustained delivery vehicle preparation of bioactive molecules. There are several advantages in 'in situ gelling system' which includes ease of application of dosage, reduced frequency of administration and even protection of drug from change in environmental conditions (Nisha *et al.*, 2014; Suisha *et al.*, 1998).

Various natural and synthetic polymers undergo in situ gel forming and potentially can be used for oral, ocular, transdermal, buccal, intraperitoneal, parenteral, injectable, rectal and vaginal routes. Recent advances in in situ gels have made it possible to exploit the changes in physiological uniqueness in different regions of the Gastrointestinal tract for improved drug absorption as well as patient's convenience and compliance. Pectin, gellan gum, chitosan, alginic acid, guar gum, carbopol, xyloglucan, xanthan gum, HPMC, poloxamer etc are some of natural polymers used for in situ gelling system. There are several applications and advantages of in situ gelling system in today's life. This review mainly focus on introduction to in situ gel, its mechanism, various polymers used and its applications (Miyazaki *et al.*, 2003; Nerkar *et al.*, 2013).

Mechanism of in situ gel

The in situ gel system's formation is done by two mechanisms such as physical mechanism and chemical mechanism.

1] Physical Mechanism:

In situ formation based on physical mechanism consists of the following:

a) Diffusion

Diffusion is a type physical approach that is used in insitu gel formulation. In this method involves the diffusion of solvent from polymer solution into surrounding tissue which results in formation of precipitation or solidification of polymer matrix. N-methyl pyrrolidone (NMP) has been commonly used polymer in formation of in-situ gelling system.

b) Swelling

Swelling is a type of physical approach that is used in insitu formulation. In this method the polymer are surrounding the polymer imbibe and the fluids that are present in exterior environment and swell from out to inside and drug releases slowly. myverol (glycerol monooleate) is a substance which is used as polar lipid that swells in water to form Lyotropic liquid crystalline phase structures. This substance has some bioadhesive properties and it can degrade in vivo by enzymatic action (Motto *et al.*, 2000).

2] Chemical Mechanism

In situ gelling formation based on chemical reactions mechanism. Chemical reactions that results in situ gelation may involve the following processes:

a) Enzymatic cross-linking

Enzymatic cross linking is the most suitable method used in formation of in situ gelling system. In this method, gel is formed by cross linking with the enzymes which are present in body fluids. In situ formation induce by natural enzymes and that are not been investigated widely but appear to have some advantages over chemical and photochemical methods. For example, an enzymatic process handles efficacy under physiologic conditions and no need for possibly destructive chemicals such as monomers and initiators. Hydrogels are used in intelligent stimuli-responsive delivery systems that can release insulin have been investigated. Modify the amount of enzyme also maintain a suitable mechanism for controlling the rate of gel formation, which confess the mixtures to be injected before gel formation (Guo *et al.*, 1998).

b) Photo-polymerization

In photo-polymerization method electromagnetic radiations are used during formation of in situ gelling system. A solution of reactive macromere or monomers and invader can be injected into a tissues site and the application of electromagnetic radiation used to form gel.

The most suitable polymers for photo polymerization are the polymers which undergo dissociation by polymerisable functional group in the presence of photo initiator like acrylate or similar monomers and macromers that are typically long wavelength ultraviolet and visible wavelengths are used. Short wavelength ultraviolet are not used often because they are limited penetration of tissue and biologically harmful. In this method, ketone, such as 2,2 dimethoxy-2-phenyl acetophenone, is used as the initiator for ultraviolet photo- polymerization. camphorquinone and ethyl eosin initiators are used in visible light systems (Podual *et al.*, 2000).

c) Ionic cross linking

In this method, the ion sensitive polymer is used. Ion sensitive polymers may undergo phase transition in presence of various ions like Na⁺, K⁺

, Ca⁺, and Mg⁺. Some polysaccharides are also in the class of ion-sensitive ones. While k-carrageenan forms rigid, small amount of K⁺ are reply in brittle gels, elastic gels are forms in icarrageenam mainly in the presence of Ca²⁺. Gellan gum mainly available as Gelrite. It is an anionic polysaccharide, in the presence of mono and divalent cations that undergoes in situ gelling system (Burkoth and Anseth, 2000; Sawhney *et al.*, 1995).

Various approaches of in situ gelation

Various approaches are made in order to get in situ gelation system:

Temperature triggered in situ gel

Temperature is the most widely used stimulus in environmentally responsive polymer systems in in-situ gelling formulation. The change of temperature used in easy to control, and also easily applicable both in vitro and in vivo. In this system, gelation is caused due to body temperature and no need of external heat. These hydrogels are liquid at room temperature (20–25°C) and undergo gelation when in contact with body fluids (35– 37°C), due to an increase in temperature. There are three types of temperature induced systems. They are negatively thermo sensitive type Eg: Poly (Nisopropylacrylamide) positively thermo sensitive type Eg: polyacrylic acid thermally reversible type Eg: poloxamer, pluronics, Tetronics.

In this system, thermo responsive or temperature responsive polymers are used that show a drastic and discontinuous change in their physical properties with temperature. These polymers show a miscibility gap at high or low temperature an upper or lower critical solution temperature exists.

pH triggered in situ gelation

In this system gel is formed due to pH changes. In this method pH sensitive polymers or pH responsive are used. In pH sensitive polymers includes pendant acidic or basic groups that may accept or release protons in counter to changes in environmental pH. The large number polymers of ionizable groups are known as poly electrolytes. The poly electrolytes are present in the formulation causes increase in external pH that leads to swelling of hydrogel that forms in situ gel. Some suitable polymers for this approach those polymers having anionic groups. Some are cellulose acetate phthalate (CAP), carbomer and its derivatives, polyethylene glycol (PEG), pseudo latexes and poly methacrylic acid (PMC) etc (Hoffman *et al.*, 1986).

Ion activated in situ gelation

In this method, gelling of the solution instilled is triggered by change in the ionic strength. It is

assumed that the rate of gelation depend on the osmotic gradient across the surface of the gel. The polymer which shows osmotically induced gelation is Gelrite or Gellan gum, Hyaluronic acid and Alginates etc (Lin and Sung, 2000).

Polymers used as in situ gelling agents

Pectin

Pectins are a family of polysaccharides, in which the polymer contains mainly, comprises α - (1-4)-- D galacturonic acid residues. In the presence of free calcium ions, Low methoxy pectins (degree of esterification <50%) readily forms gels in aqueous solution, which crosslink the galacturonic acid chains in a manner described by egg-box model. In the presence of H⁺ ions the gelation of pectin will occur, a source of divalent ions, generally calcium ions is required to produce the gels that are suitable as vehicles for drug delivery. Pectin used mainly for these formulations is that it is water soluble, so organic solvents are not used in the formulation. Divalent cations present in the stomach, carry out the transition of pectin to gel state when it is orally administered (Miyazaki and Kawasaki, 2001).

Guar gum Properties

Guar gum is also called as guaran of naturally occurring gum which is obtained from the endosperm of the seed. Guar gum is insoluble in hydrocarbons, fats, esters, alcohols and ketones but soluble in water. These show its dispersibility in both cold and hot water that it is soluble in both cold and hot water to form colloidal solution at low amount.

Guar gum has derivatives are used in targeted delivery systems in the formation of coating matrix systems, nano-microparticles and hydrogels. Guar gum also has derivatives such as graft polymers like polyacrylamide grafted guar gums that have good colon targeting properties. It can also be used as a polymer in matrix tablets which shows controlled release (Kokate *et al.*, 2008; Davies *et al.*, 1991).

Carbopol Properties

Carbopol is a polyacrylic acid (PAA) polymer, which changed to gel as the pH is raised from 4.0 to 7.4. Carbopol remains in solution form at acidic pH but transform into a low viscosity gel at alkaline pH. HPMC is used in combination with carbopol which enhance viscosity of carbopol solution, while reducing the acidity of the solution. Comparing different types of poly (acrylic acid) (Carbopol 940-934-941and 910) 47 concluded that Carbopol 940 showed superior appearance and clarity (Shastri and Patel, 2010).

Xyloglucan Properties

Xyloglucan is also called as tamarind gum which is a polysaccharide obtained from the endosperm of the seed. Xyloglucan consists of three different oligomers like heptasaccharide, octasaccharide, nonsaccharide, which differ in number of galactose side chain. It is mainly used in oral, rectal, ocular drug delivery due to its non-toxic, biodegradable and biocompatible property. Like, poloxamer it exhibits gelation on heating refrigerator temperature or cooling from a higher temperature (Miyazaki *et al.*, 2001; Grasdalen and Smidsroed, 1987).

Gellan gum Properties

Gellan gum is an anionic hetero polysaccharide, secreted by microbe *Sphingomonas elodea*. It consists of glucose, rhamnose, glucuronic acid and linked together to obtain a tetrasaccharide unit. Gelrite is deacetylated gellan gum, obtained by treating gellan gum with alkali to remove the acetyl group in the molecule. Due to instillation, gelrite forms gel because in presence of calcium ions. The gelation includes the formation of double helical junction zones followed by aggregation of double helical segment to form three dimensional networks by complexation with cations and hydrogen bonding with water. In food industry, gellan gum is used as suspending and stabilizing agent (Miyazaki *et al.*, 1998; Sechoy *et al.*, 2000).

Alginic acid Properties

It is a linear block copolymer polysaccharide consists of β D-mannuronic acid and α -L-glucuronic acid residues joined by 1,4-glycosidic linkages. In each block and the arrangement of blocks along the molecule vary depending on the algal source. Dilute aqueous solutions of alginates form firm gels on addition of diandtrivalent metal ions by a cooperative process involves consecutive glucuronic residues in the α -L glucuronic acid blocks of the alginate chain. Alginic acid used as a vehicle for ophthalmic formulations, since it exhibits favorable biological properties such as biodegradable and non toxic (Cohen *et al.*, 1997).

Xanthum gum Properties

Xanthan gum has high molecular weight extra cellular polysaccharide which is produced by the fermentation of the gram-negative bacterium *Xanthomonas campestris*. The primary structure of this naturally produced cellulose derivative contains a cellulosic backbone (β -D-glucose residues) and a trisaccharide side chain of β -D-mannose β -D-glucuronic acid- α -D-mannose attached with alternate glucose residues of the main chain. Xanthan gum is soluble in cold and hot water as well as alkaline and acidic conditions. It exhibits good stability at alkaline conditions (Grant *et al.*, 1973).

Chitosan Properties

Gelling of chitosan occurs by two changes such as pH responsive change and temperature change. Chitosan is a natural component of shrimp and crab shell which consist of biodegradable, thermosensitive, polycationic polymer obtained by alkaline deacetylation of chitin. Chitosan is a biocompatible pH dependent cationic polymer, which can remain dissolved in aqueous solutions up to a pH of 6.2. Neutralization of chitosan aqueous solution to a pH exceeding 6.2 leads to precipitation by the formation of a hydrated gel (Shamklani *et al.*, 1991).

HPMC Properties

Cellulose consists of glucan chain which has repeating β -(1, 4)-D-glucopyranose unit. Some natural polymers like HPMC, MC and EC these exhibit temperature sensitive sol-gel phase transition. Cellulose material will increase its viscosity when temperature decreases while its derivatives like HPMC, MC, will also increase its viscosity when temperature is increased. MC is a natural polymer composed of native cellulose with alternate methyl substitution group on its chain. At low temperature (300 C) solution is in liquid form and when temperature increases (40-500 C) and gelation occurred (Chenite *et al.*, 2000).

Poloxamer Properties

Poloxamer are water soluble tri-block copolymer. It consists of two polyethylene oxide (PEO) and polypropylene oxide (PPO) core in an ABA configuration (Calonge, 2011).

Poloxamer is commercially available as Pluronic and has good thermal setting property and increased drug residence time. It mainly used as gelling agent, emulsifying agent and solubilizing agent. Poloxamer gives colourless, transparent gel. It depends upon the ratio and distribution of hydrophilic and hydrophobic chain several molecular weights available, having different gelling property (Nanjawade *et al.*, 2007).

Applications of in situ polymeric drug delivery system

Oral drug delivery system

The pH-sensitive hydro gels have a potential use in sitespecific delivery of drugs to specific regions of the GI tract. Hydro gels built of varying proportions of cross linked PEG and PAA derivatives allowed in preparing silicone microspheres, which produce prednisolone in the gastric medium or showed gastro protective property. Cross-linked dextran hydro gels with a faster swelling under high pH conditions, whereas other polysaccharides such as amidated pectin's, inulin and guar gum were investigated in order to improve a potential colon-specific drug delivery

system. The formulations of gellan and sodium alginate both contain a complexed calcium ion that undergoes a process of gelation by releasing of these ions in the acidic environment of the stomach.

Ocular drug delivery system

In ocular delivery system natural polymers like alginic acid, inulin, & xyloglucan, inulin are most commonly used. For local ophthalmic delivery system different compounds such as autonomic drugs, anti-inflammatory agent & antimicrobial agent, are used to release intra ocular tension in glaucoma. Conventional delivery system often result in poor availability & therapeutic response due to high tear fluid turn over & dynamics leads rapid elimination of the drug from the eye so, the overcome the bioavailability problem ophthalmic in-situ gel were developed. To improve the bioavailability viscosity enhancers such as Carboxy Methyl Cellulose, Hydroxy Propyl Methyl Cellulose, Carbomers, Poly Vinyl alcohol used to improve the viscosity of formulation in order to prolong the precorneal residence time & increases the bioavailability, easy to manufacture. Penetration enhancer such as preservatives, chelating agent, surfactants are used to develop corneal drug penetration.

Nasal drug delivery system

In nasal in-situ gel system xanthan gum and gellan gum are used as in-situ gel forming polymers. Mometasone furoate used to evaluate for its efficacy for the treatment of allergic rhinitis. Animal study is used to conduct allergic rhinitis model & effect of in-situ gel on antigen induced nasal symptoms in sensitized rats was observed. In-situ gel was found to inhibit the increase in nasal symptoms are compared to marketed preparation nosonex (Mometasone furoate suspension 0.05%).

Rectal and vaginal drug delivery system

The rectal route may be used to deliver many types of drugs that are formulated as liquid, semisolid (ointments, creams and foams) and solid dosage forms (suppositories). Acetaminophen an anti-inflammatory drug formulated as rectal in situ gel by using polycarbophil and poloxamer F188 and poloxamer 407 as synthetic polymer forming in situ gelling liquid suppository which is considered as an synthetic polymers forming in situ gelling liquid suppository which is considered as an effective method shows enhance bioavailability (Ramesh *et al.*, 2001).

Injectable drug delivery system

In this drug delivery system are also formulated as in situ gels which obtained over the last decade due to its uses as there is no surgical procedure is required and also patient compliance. Mostly

synthetic polymers and block copolymers are used in the formulation of injectable in situ gel. One example of inflammatory drug is Bupivacaine which is formulated as a injectable in situ gel using poly(D,L-lactide), poly (D,L-lactide coglycolide) and PLGA as polymer shows prolong action drug in gel conditions.

Dermal and transdermal drug delivery

Pluronic F127 in thermally reversible gel was evaluated as vehicle for the percutaneous administration of Indomethacin. In-vivo studies suggest that 20% w/w aqueous gel may be it is used as practical base for topical administration of the drug. The combination of iontophoresis and chemical enhancers resulted in synergistic enhancement of insulin permeation.

Evaluation and characterization of in situ gels systems

In situ gels may be evaluated and characterized for the following parameters;

Viscosity and Rheology

This is a crucial parameter to consider when evaluating in situ gels. A Brookfield rheometer or another type of viscometer can be used to test the viscosity and rheological parameters of in situ forming drug delivery systems. These formulations' viscosity should be such that no issues are anticipated during patient administration, particularly parenteral and ocular administration (Rozier *et al.*, 1989; Smart *et al.*, 1984).

Sol-Gel Transition Temperature and Gelling Time

The sol-gel transition temperature can be defined as the temperature at which the phase transition of the sol meniscus is first detected when retained in a sample tube at a certain temperature and then heated at a specified pace for in situ gel forming systems comprising thermoreversible polymers. The absence of movement of the meniscus when the tube is tilted indicates gel formation (Jeong *et al.*, 1999; Haglund *et al.*, 1996).

Gel Strength

A rheometer can be used to test this parameter. A specific amount of gel is prepared in a beaker from the sol form, depending on the mechanism of the gelling agent used. This gel-containing beaker is lifted at a set rate, allowing you to slowly push a probe into the gel. The load on the probe can be quantified as a function of the probe's depth of immersion below the gel surface (Chandrashekar and Udupa, 1998; Cao *et al.*, 2009).

In vitro Drug Release Studies

The plastic dialysis cell is used to conduct drug release experiments for in situ gel formulations that

will be delivered by oral, ocular, or rectal routes. The formulation's sol form is deposited in the donor compartment. In an incubator, the constructed cell is shook horizontally. Analytical techniques are used to examine the receptor solution for drug release. The formulation is poured into vials containing receptor media and placed on a shaker water bath at the desired temperature and oscillations rate for injectable in situ gels. Periodically, samples are taken and evaluated.

Fourier Transform Infra-red Spectroscopy and Thermal Analysis

Using the potassium bromide pellet approach, the nature of interacting forces can be determined during the gelation process. The percentage of water in hydrogel can be determined by thermogravimetric measurement for in situ forming polymeric systems. Differential scanning calorimetry is used to see if there are any thermogram changes when compared to the pure constituents, indicating interactions (Wang *et al.*, 2007).

Texture Analysis

The firmness, consistency, and cohesiveness of hydrogels are evaluated using a texture analyzer, which primarily shows the syringeability of the sol, allowing the formulation to be injected in vivo with ease (Chen and Jagdish, 2005; Kevin *et al.*, 2013).

CONCLUSION:

In conclusion, increasing patient compliance is the key prerequisite of a successful controlled release product, which in situ gels provide. The use of polymeric in situ gels for controlled drug release offers a number of benefits over traditional dosage forms. The in situ gel dosage forms are particularly trustworthy due to the drug's sustained and prolonged release, as well as its good stability and biocompatibility.

In situ gel formulations that use biodegradable and water soluble polymers can be more acceptable and effective drug delivery strategies. In situ gel preparations have the potential to be more effective than a traditional liquid dosing form. When compared to traditional dosage forms, they have higher patient acceptance and compliance and may offer superior biopharmaceutical characteristics, improved efficacy, prolonged drug administration, and improved safety. Because of the availability of new technology, as well as high market acceptability and patient demand, the potential for such a dosage form is encouraging. With the continuing development of new pharmaceutical products, more novel in situ gel technologies are likely to emerge in the future.

REFERENCE:

1. Nisha Patel, Gajanan Shinde and Rajesh KS. Ophthalmic In situ gel, A genesis journal Pharmagene, 2(4), 2014, 29-33.
2. F. Suisha, N. Kawasaki, S. Miyazaki, M. Shirakawa, K. Yamatoya, M. Sasaki, D. Attwood, Xyloglucan gels as sustained release vehicles for the intraperitoneal administration of mitomycin C. Int. J. Pharm., 172, 1998, 27-32
3. Miyazaki S, Endo K, Kawasaki N, Kubo W, Watanabe H, Attwood D. Oral sustained delivery of paracetamol from in situ gelling xyloglucan formulations. Drug Dev Ind. Pharm., 29(2), 2003, 113-9.
4. Nerkar Tushar, Gujarathi Nayan A, Rane Bhushan R, Bakliwal Sunil R, Pawar S.P. In situ gel: Novel Approach in sustained and controlled drug delivery system. International Journal of Pharmaceutical sciences, 4(4), 2013, 1-18.
5. Motto F, Gailloud P, *et al.*, In-vitro assessment of new embolic liquids prepared from preformed polymers and water miscible solvents aneurysm treatment. Biomaterials, 21, 2000, 803-11.
6. Guo J-H, Skinner GW, Harcum WW, Barnum PE. Pharmaceutical applications of naturally occurring watersoluble polymers. Pharm Sci & Technol Today, 1, 1998, 254- 61.
7. Podual K, Doyle III FJ, Peppas NA. Dynamic behavior of glucose oxidase-containing microparticles of poly (ethylene)- grafted cationic hydrogels in an environment of changing pH. Biomaterials, 21, 2000, 1439-50.
8. Burkoth AK, Anseth KS. A review of photocrosslinked polyanhydrides: In situ forming degradable networks. Biomaterials, 21, 2000, 2395-404.
9. Sawhney AS, Pathak CP, Hubbell JA, Hill JL, Desai NP. Photopolymerizable biodegradable hydrogels as tissue contacting materials and controlled release carriers. US Patent 5410016. 1995.
10. Hoffman A.S., Afrassiabi A, Dong L.C. Thermally reversible hydrogels: II. Delivery and selective removal of substances from aqueous solutions. J. Control. Release, 4, 1986, 213- 222.
11. Hong – Ru Lin, K. C. Sung. Carbopol/Pluronic phase change solutions for ophthalmic drug delivery. Journal of Controlled Release. 69, 2000, 379-388.
12. Miyazaki S, Kawasaki N. Comparison of in situ gelling formulations for the oral delivery of cimetidine. Int J Pharm, 220, 2001, 161-8.
13. Kokate C.K., Purohit A. P., Gokhale S.B. Pharmacognoc. 14th Ed. Published by Nirali Prakashan, 137, 2008, 141,146,152.

14. Davies N.M., Farr S.J., Hadgraft J., Kellaway L.W. Evaluation of mucoadhesive polymers in ocular drug delivery. I. Viscous solutions, *Pharm. Res.*, 8(8), 1991, 1039–1043.
15. Shastri DH, Patel LD, Novel alternative to ocular drug delivery system: Hydrogel, *Ind J Pharma Res*, 2010; 2: 1-13.
16. Miyazaki S, Suzuki S, Kawasaki N, Endo K, Takahashi A, Attwood D, In situ gelling xyloglucan formulations for sustained release ocular delivery of pilocarpine hydrochloride. *Int J Pharm*, 229, 2001, 29-36.
17. Grasdalen H, Smidsroed O. Gelation of gellan gum. *Carbohydrate Polymers*, 7, 1987, 371-93.
18. Miyazaki S, Suisha F, Kawasaki N, Shirakawa M, Yamatoya K, Attwood K, Thermally reversible xyloglucan gels as vehicles for rectal drug delivery, *J Control Rel*, 56, 1998, 75-83.
19. Sechoy O, Tissie G, Sebastian C, Maurin F, Driot JY, Trinquand C. A new long acting ophthalmic formulation of carteolol containing Alginate acid. *Int J Pharm*, 207, 2000, 109-16.
20. Cohen S., Lobel E., Trevigoda A., Peled Y. A novel in-situ forming Ophthalmic drug delivery system from alginates undergoing gelation in the eye. *Journal of Controlled Release.*, 44, 1997, 201-208.
21. Grant G.T., Morris E.R., Rees D.A., Smith P.J.C., Thom D. Biological interactions between polysaccharides and divalent cations: The egg box model. *FEBS Lett.*, 32, 1973, 195-198.
22. Al-Shamklani A, Bhakoo M, Tuboku MA, Duncan R. Evaluation of the biological properties of alginates and gellan and xanthan gum. *Proc Int Symp Control Release Bioact Mater*, 18, 1991, 213-4.
23. Chenite A, Chaput C, Wang D, Combes C, Buschmann MD, Hoemann CD *et al.* Novel injectable solution of chitosan form biodegradable gels in situ. *Biomaterials*, 21, 2000, 2155-61.
24. Calonge M, The treatment of dry eye, *Surv Ophthalmol*, 45, 2011, 227-239.
25. Nanjawade BK, Manvi FV, Manjappa AS, Review of in-situ forming hydrogels for sustained ophthalmic drug delivery, *J Control Rel*, 122, 2007, 119-134.
26. Ramesh CR, Zentner GM, Jeong B. Macro med, Inc. Biodegradable low molecular weight triblock poly (lactideco- glycolide) polyethylene glycolcopolymers having reverse thermal gelation properties. US patent 6201072. 2001.
27. Rozier A, Mazuel C, Grove J, Plazonnet B. Gelrite: A novel, ion activated, In situ gelling polymer for ophthalmic vehicles: Effect on bioavailability of Timolol. *Int J Pharm*. 1989;57:163–8.
28. Smart JD, Kellaway IW, Worthington HE. An in vivo investigation of mucosa adhesive materials for use in controlled drug delivery. *J Pharm Pharmacol*. 1984;36:259–99.
29. Jeong B, Choi YK, Bae YH, Zentner G, Kim SW. New biodegradable polymers for injectable drug delivery system. *J Control Release*. 1999;62:109–14.
30. Haglund BO, Rajashree J, Kenneth JH. An in situ gelling system for parenteral delivery. *J Control Release*. 1996;41:229–35.
31. Chandrashekhar G, Udupa N. Biodegradable injectable implant system for long term drug delivery using poly (lactic-co-glycolic) acid copolymers. *J Pharm Pharmacol*. 1998;48:669–74.
32. Cao S, Ren X, Zhang Q, Chen E, Xu F, Chen J, et al. In situ gel based on gellan gum as new carrier for nasal administration of mometasonefuroate. *Int J Pharm*. 2009;365:109–15.
33. Wu J, Wei W, Wang LY, Su ZG, Ma G. A thermosensitive hydrogel based on quaternized chitosan and poly (ethylene glycol) for nasal delivery system. *Biomaterials*. 2007;28:2220–32.
34. Chen S, Jagdish S. Controlled delivery of testosterone from smart polymer solution based systems: In vitro evaluation. *Int J Pharm*. 2005;295:183–90.
35. Kevin Garala, Parth Joshi, Malay Shah, A Ramkishan, Jaydeep Patel, Formulation and evaluation of periodontal in situ gel, *International Journal of Pharmaceutical investigation* 2013;3(1):29–41.